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An Analysis of the Last Decade of Foreign Tourism in Alanya; The Effects of Political Crises and the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the impact of the aircraft crisis with Russia and the Covid-19 pandemic on foreign tourism in Alanya, a district of Antalya Province of Türkiye over the past decade and to provide recommendations for potential similar crises in the future. The arrival of foreign tourists to Alanya is mainly by air transportation, and any interruption in air transportation causes disruption of all activities within the scope of foreign tourism. Alanya has experienced significant losses in foreign tourism in past decade, especially as a result of the aircraft crisis between Türkiye and Russia in 2015, when Russia did not allow tourist flights to Türkiye and air transportation almost came to a halt within the scope of the Covid-19 pandemic between 2019-2021. This study aims to determine the impact of the air crisis with Russia and the Covid-19 pandemic on foreign tourism in Alanya over the past decade and to provide recommendations for potential similar crises in the future. To achieve this goal, official tourism and air transport statistics between 2011-2022 were examined, and historical data analysis was conducted. The study provides information about Alanya's geographical location, population, and the inception of tourism activities while presenting and evaluating detailed tourism and air transport statistics for Alanya over the past 10 years. Accordingly, this study, utilizes a systematic approach, sourcing data from official reports and databases, with a primary focus on data from the Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Culture and Tourism, supplemented by other sources like the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), the Turkish State Airports Authority (DHMI) and the Alanya Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ALTSO). Descriptive statistics unveil key data patterns, while qualitative data from academic literature, government reports and news sources provide insights into Alanya's responses to political crises. Accordingly, this study reveals a comprehensive understanding of how crises affect Alanya's air transport and tourism and offers suggestions for dealing with similar crises that are likely to occur in the future.

Keywords: Alanya, Foreign Tourism, Political Crises, Covid-19, Tourism Transportation

Alanya Dış Turizminin Son On Yılına İlişkin Bir Analiz; Siyasi Krizlerin ve Kovid-19 Pandemisinin Etkileri

Özet

Bu çalışma, son on yılda Türkiye'de yer alan Antalya ilinin Alanya İlçesinin' yabancı turizmi üzerindeki Rusya ile yaşanan uçak krizi ve Kovid-19 pandemisinin etkisini belirlemeyi ve gelecekteki benzer

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krizler için öneriler sunmayı amaçlamaktadır. Alanya'ya yabancı turistlerin gelişleri esas olarak hava ulaşımı ile olup hava ulaşımının aksaması yabancı turizmi kapsamındaki tüm faaliyetlerin aksamasına neden olmaktadır. Alanya, geçtiğimiz on yıl içinde, özellikle 2015 yılındaki Türkiye ile Rusya arasında yaşanan uçak krizi sonucu Rusya'nın Türkiye'ye yönelik turistik uçak seferlerine izin vermemesi ve 2019-2021 yılları arasındaki Covid-19 pandemisi kapsamında hava ulaşımının neredeyse durma noktasına gelmesiyle yabancı turizmde çok önemli kayıplar yaşamıştır. Bu çalışma, Alanya'da turizm ve turizm ulaşımı açısından bu tür kriz dönemlerinde yaşanan olumsuzlukları incelemekte ve gelecekte benzerlerinin yaşanmaması için öneriler sunmaktadır. Bu amaca ulaşmak için, 2011-2022 yılları arasında yayımlanan resmi turizm ve hava ulaşımı istatistikleri incelenmiş ve tarihsel veri analizleri yapılmıştır. Çalışma ile Alanya'nın coğrafi konumu, nüfusu, ulaşım ve turizm faaliyetleri hakkında genel bilgi sunulmuş ve son 10 yılı ait detaylı hava ulaşım ve turizm istatistikleri değerlendirilmiştir. Bu bağlamda, çalışmada, Türkiye Cumhuriyeti Kültür ve Turizm Bakanlığı başta olmak üzere resmi raporlar ve veri tabanları veri kaynakları olarak kullanılmış, bu veriler Dünya Turizm Örgütü (UNWTO), Devlet Hava Meydanları İşletmesi Genel Müdürlüğü (DHMI) ve Alanya Ticaret ve Sanayi Odası (ALTSO) gibi diğer kaynaklar ile desteklenmiştir. Tanımlayıcı istatistikler, anahtar veri desenlerini açığa çıkarırken, akademik literatür, hükümet raporları ve haber kaynaklarından elde edilen veriler Alanya'nın krizlere verdiği yanıtları anlamamıza yardımcı olmuştur. Bu kapsamda bu çalışma, krizlerin Alanya'nın turizm ulaşımı ve turizmine nasıl etki ettiğine dair kapsamlı bir anlayışı ortaya koymakta ve gelecekte yaşanması muhtemel benzer krizlerle başa çıkmak için öneriler sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Alanya, Yabancı Turizm, Politik Krizler, Covid-19, Turizm Ulaştırması.

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines tourism as “a social, cultural and economic phenomenon which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/professional purposes” (Glossary of Tourism Terms |UNWTO, n.d.). Tourism, particularly in developing countries, can provide important contributions to economic and social development. Especially since 1980's, tourism has made important contributions in both senses in Türkiye (Okuyucu, 2013).

Transport is a crucial element of tourism. It is one of the four key factors along with resorts, tourist behavior and the attitudes of decision makers. Transport is shown to play a key role in opening up a destination: the links between transport and an increasing number of resorts intensify, excursion circuits develop and in the last phase a situation of maximum connectivity results (Lohmann & Pearce, 2012). Travel time is an important element in adopting the holiday decision in the option for a particular destination, especially in international tourism. It is mainly by the reason of the improvement of transportation that tourism has expanded (Dinu, 2018). As a result of rapid increase in air transportation activities after the 1980s, tourism and air transportation have become two important sectors that depend on and support each other. Today, air transport is certainly the most significant component of the long-haul travel. Being the fastest mode of transportation, it is most suitable means where time is an important factor, as in tourism activities (Dileep & Kurien, 2022). In particular, the

desire and reality of minimizing time in transportation to holiday resorts at distance of 2.000 km. or more, brings air transportation to the fore (Doğaner, 1998).

Tourism is one of the most sensitive industries across risks and crises based on economic, social and political developments. In recent years, the challenges as terrorism, epidemics and economic blockades based on political tension between countries not only cause increased risks and threats on destinations but also cause decreased touristic mobility (Pelit et al., 2022). Hence, the tourism industry, as an open system, must pursue to adapt to its surroundings in order to continue its existence.

With this in mind, an analysis of the last decade of foreign tourism in Alanya illustrates the extent of the effects of politics, economics and crises to Turkish tourism and air transport industry and in general provides a mirror to the tourism industry as a whole.

Internationally, the travel and tourism industry stands as a pivotal sector, renowned for its substantial contributions to employment generation, socio-economic advancement, and cultural enrichment on a global scale (Abbas et al., 2021). Moreover, as an open and organic system, the tourism industry has always been affected by both the micro and macro environment. Hence, the tourism industry, as an open system, must pursue to adapt to its surroundings in order to continue its existence. In consideration of this aspect, an analysis of the last decade of foreign tourism in Alanya illustrates the extent of the effects of politics, economics and crises to Turkish tourism industry and in general provides a mirror to the tourism industry as a whole.

The development of tourism activities in the world began after the 1950s, and has become an important developing sector in recent years. Air transportation, which developed rapidly in the same period, also made a great contribution to this. The annual tourist circulation was around 25 million in the 1950s and it exceeded 500 million in the 1990s and 1 billion in 2011 (Türkiye Seyahat Acentaları Birliği (TÜRSAB), 2020). Tourism mobility in the world increased by approximately 4% to 5% from 2011 to 2015 and 6% to 7% from 2016 to 2019 annually. The number of international tourists rose to 1,46 billion in 2019 but it decreased unprecedentedly by 74% to 380 million in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic (Table-1). In Europe, which has a 50% share in the world tourism market, the number of tourists increased to 742 million in 2019 but it decreased by 70% to 240 million in 2020. Türkiye ranked sixth after France, Spain, the USA, China and Italy among countries hosting the highest number of tourists. After the Pandemic, world and European tourism mobility increased respectively to 595 and 969 million respectively in 2021 and 2022 (World Tourism Organization, 2022).

According to the data of the last decade, Türkiye's annual share in the world tourism market is approximately 3,5 to 3,7 percent. In parallel with the tourism mobility in the world, Türkiye also experienced significant increases from 2011 to 2019. The number of international tourists increased from approximately 37 million in 2011 to 52 million in 2019. Türkiye's annual share of the European tourist market was approximately 7% from 2011 to 2019 except the Russian crisis period (World Tourism Organization, 2011; World Tourism Organization, 2012; World Tourism Organization, 2013; World Tourism Organization, 2014; World Tourism Organization, 2015; World Tourism Organization, 2016; World Tourism Organization, 2017; World Tourism Organization, 2022).

Following the pandemic, in 2021 and 2022, Türkiye's tourist mobility increased faster than the world average, reaching 51.4 million in 2022, and in this context, its share in world tourism mobility increased to 8-9%.

Table 1: 2011-2022 World International Tourism; Number of Arrivals

Year	World	Europe	Europe /World	Türkiye	Türkiye /Europe	Türkiye/ World
2011	982.000.000	504.000.000	51,32	36.769.039	7,30	3,74
2012	1.035.000.000	534.000.000	51,59	37.715.225	7,06	3,64
2013	1.087.000.000	563.000.000	51,79	39.860.771	7,08	3,67
2014	1.135.000.000	584.000.000	53,70	41.627.248	7,13	3,67
2015	1.184.000.000	609.000.000	51,44	41.114.069	6,75	3,47
2016	1.235.000.000	615.000.000	49,80	30.906.680	5,03	2,50
2017	1.323.000.000	671.000.000	51,00	37.969.824	5,66	2,87
2018	1.400.000.000	710.000.000	50,71	46.112.592	6,49	3,29
2019	1.464.000.000	742.000.000	51,04	51.747.199	6,94	3,54
2020	407.000.000	240.000.000	58,96	15.971.201	6,65	3,92
2021	458.000.000	301.000.000	65,72	30.038.961	9,98	6,62
2022	969.000.000	595.000.000	61,40	51.387.513	8,64	5,30

Source: UNWTO, 2011; UNWTO, 2012; UNWTO, 2013; UNWTO, 2014; UNWTO, 2015; UNWTO, 2016; UNWTO, 2017; UNWTO, 2022.

The development in world air transportation after 1950 is as follows: According to the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) data, world commercial passenger traffic exceeded 31 million passengers in 1950 (ICAO, 1951), 515 million in 1974 (ICAO,

1982), 1 billion in 1988, 2 billion in 2005, 3 billion in 2012 and 4 billion in 2017 (ICAO, 1951; ICAO 1982; ICAO, 1989; ICAO, 2006; ICAO, 2003; ICAO, 2017).

In the context of the Covid-19 Pandemic, which started in late 2019, there were significant decreases in passenger traffic. In 2022, there was an increase of 47% compared to 2021, and it is predicted that the 2019 values will be reached again or even exceeded in 2023 (Graphic 1).

Graphic 1: World Total Scheduled Air Passenger Traffic (2000-2022)

Source: ICAO Statistics; 2000-2022.

Türkiye's domestic-international-total passenger traffic values between 2011-2022 are shown below in Graphic 2. As can be seen from the graph, passenger traffic, which has been on a steady increase since 2011, decreased significantly in 2020 and 2021 due to the Covid 19 pandemic in 2019, and started to increase again as of 2022. In 2023, total passenger traffic is expected to exceed 2010 million passengers. The reason for the partial decrease in 2016, is the aircraft crises with Russia (DHMI, 2012; DHMI, 2013; DHMI, 2014; DHMI, 2015; DHMI, 2016; DHMI, 2017; DHMI, 2018; DHMI, 2019; DHMI, 2020; DHMI, 2021).

Graphic 2: Türkiye Total Air Passenger Traffic (2011-2022)

Source: DHMİ, 2012; DHMİ, 2013; DHMİ, 2014; DHMİ, 2015; DHMİ, 2016; DHMİ, 2017; DHMİ, 2018; DHMİ, 2019; DHMİ, 2020; DHMİ, 2021.

Within this framework, this article first analyzes the development of tourism activities specifically in Alanya within the framework of Türkiye's tourism industry to put forth the density of the repercussions of events of the last decade, specifically the aircraft crisis with Russia and Covid-19. Hence, in overall the aim of this study is to analyze how Alanya has been affected and how the city has responded to the two main crises of the last decade in accordance to statistical data. Further, a general outlook of the industry will be used as a guide to forecast what the future holds for tourism in Alanya. This analysis thus will create recommendations for a more sustainable tourism retrospect the last decade.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Tourism is increasingly viewed as an attractive development option for parts of the developing world. Almost all countries are seeking the potential benefits of tourism, such as increased income, foreign exchange, employment and economic diversification (Sharpley & Telfer, 2008). Tourism significantly shapes the global economy, including Türkiye. The travel and tourism industry in the time of service-led growth trends has become increasingly important worldwide since 1990. From 1995, the travel and tourism industry's direct contribution to the world GDP increased from 9,9% in 1995 to 10,3% in 2019 (Škare et al., 2021). Although an important global economic sector, tourism is very vulnerable to crisis from any country or region of the world. Furthermore, it is highly sensitive to security problems, economic crises and health problems due to its postponable structure (Blake & Sinclair, 2003). Crises and the way they underline global tourism have proven to be temporarily troublesome and instead, have tended to induce short and

medium-term disruption (Cheer et al., 2021). But, it has never been affected by any crisis as much it has been by the Covid-19 pandemic (Demir et al., 2021).

This study constructs a comprehensive framework to analyze the dynamic forces of tourism, focusing on Alanya, a coastal city on the Mediterranean. Türkiye's tourism sector has shown substantial growth, reaching 51,8 million international visitors in 2019.

Our framework considers various factors affecting Türkiye's tourism, including global crises like the Russian aircraft crisis and Covid-19. Notably, a shift towards alternative tourism, such as ecotourism and nature/adventure travel, has emerged due to a desire for safety and solitude.

Alanya, with its rich history and diverse cultural influences, is our focal point. This study explores the interplay of historical, economic and environmental elements in shaping Alanya's tourism landscape. The objective is to furnish insights and recommendations aimed at augmenting the tourism sector in both Alanya and Türkiye holistically. This exhaustive scrutiny endeavors to proffer strategic guidance for bolstering the tourism industry. Accordingly, an analysis of tourism activities in Türkiye is presented initially, followed by a focus on the Antalya region. Subsequently, an in-depth analysis of Alanya's data is conducted.

2.1. Tourism Activities in Türkiye

Statistical data shows that the development in the tourism and air transportation sectors in Türkiye happened in parallel to each other. Tourism and air transportation have become an important input for the Türkiye's economy in recent years.

Tourism has emerged as a significant contributor to the Türkiye's economy in recent years. As evidenced in Table 4, the influx of foreign visitors to Türkiye stood at approximately 40 million in 2013, experiencing a steady rise to 51.8 million by 2019, excluding the influence of the Russian aircraft crisis. The number of foreign visitors decreased to 16 million in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Important factors decreasing the number of visitors due to the pandemic include transnational entry-exit bans, domestic travel restrictions, quarantines, canceled national/international organizations (concerts, sports competitions, fairs, etc.), curfews, etc (Acar, 2020). As mentioned above, after the Pandemic, foreign tourist mobility in Türkiye increased rapidly in 2021 and 2022, reaching 30 and 51,4 million respectively.

While Türkiye's tourism receipts were 1,8 billion US dollars in 2019, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, it was realized as 0,9 billion US dollars in 2020, and 2,1 billion US dollars in 2021, and with the increasing number of tourists in 2022, it was realized as 2,4 billion US dollars. Foreign tourists mostly prefer Istanbul, Antalya Region, Muğla (Bodrum, Marmaris) and Nevşehir (Cappadocia) in Türkiye. Foreigners preferring Türkiye have been mostly from the Russian Federation, Germany, Bulgaria, the United

Kingdom, Netherlands, Iran and Georgia. Entries from Bulgaria and Georgia are usually visiting for border trade (Sınır İstatistikleri 2011-2021, n.d.).

Diversification of tourism activities for Türkiye is not at the desired level yet and they are mostly in the form of sea and sun tourism in summer. There are ongoing efforts to extend tourism activities to 12 months by transitioning from traditional to alternative tourism. Traditional tourism is dependent on holiday seasons, aimed at large visitor groups, uses high capacity within the season, and has an unstable structure that is easily affected by economic and political crises. On the other hand, alternative tourism is extended over the whole year, long term, value-oriented, uses average capacity and is aimed at small groups (Çakır, 2018). Alternative forms of tourism in Türkiye are as follows: river-rafting tourism, hunting, mountain climbing, golf tourism, air sports, religious tourism, the Silk Road, winter tourism, congress tourism, bird watching, cave tourism, health and thermal tourism, scuba diving, yacht tourism and tableland tourism (Turizm Çeşitleri, n.d.).

The dominant tourism type in Türkiye is culture tourism in the Istanbul-Izmir area and 3S (sun-sea-sand) tourism in the Antalya area. Antalya, which is the primary center of 3S tourism in Türkiye, has weather conditions suitable for visiting in all four seasons as well as all conditions for beach and underwater sports, rafting, congress, mountain climbing, skiing, cave, tableland, gastronomy, health and religious tourism, and culture tourism in depending on its rich history and cultural heritage.

Further, the Covid-19 pandemic has affected consumer habits and preferences in tourism, revealing different tourism options. The interest in ecotourism and nature/adventure tourism has increased as people want to stay away from crowded places because of the pandemic. People have started to prefer nearby places and boutique hotels where they can go by their own vehicles and stay alone with nature. Caravan tourism and yacht renting have also increased in this period (TÜRSAB, 2020).

Table 2: 2011-2022; Distribution of Foreign Visitors Arriving in Türkiye (Total) by Countries

Years/ Countries	Russian Fed.	Germany	Bulgaria	United Kingdom	Georgia	Iran	Netherlands	Ukraine	Iraq	Others	Foreigners total	Türkiye's citizens living abroad	G. Total
2011	3.468.214	4.826.315	1.491.561	2.582.054	1.152.661	1.879.304	1.222.823	602.404	369.033	13.861.707	31.456.076	5.312.963	36.769.039
2012	3.599.925	5.028.745	1.492.073	2.456.519	1.404.882	1.186.343	1.273.593	634.663	533.149	14.172.940	31.782.832	5.932.393	37.715.225

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	4.269.306	4.409.049	3.649.003	866.256	4.715.438	5.964.613	7.017.657	2.126.758	4.694.422	5.232.611
	5.041.323	5.250.036	5.580.792	3.890.074	3.584.653	4.512.360	5.027.472	1.118.932	3.085.215	5.679.194
	1.582.912	1.693.591	1.821.480	1.690.766	1.852.867	2.386.885	2.713.464	1.242.961	1.402.795	2.882.512
	2.509.357	2.600.360	2.512.139	1.711.481	1.658.715	2.254.871	2.562.064	820.709	392.746	3.370.739
	1.769.447	1.755.289	1.911.832	2.206.266	2.438.730	2.069.392	1.995.254	410.501	291.852	1.514.813
	1.196.801	1.590.664	1.700.385	1.665.160	2.501.948	2.001.744	2.102.890	385.762	1.153.092	2.331.076
	132.466	1.303.730	1.232.487	906.336	799.006	1.013.642	1.117.290	271.526	645.641	1.244.756
	756.187	657.051	706.551	1.045.043	1.284.735	1.386.934	1.547.996	997.652	2.060.008	675.467
	730.639	857.246	1.094.144	420.831	896.876	1.172.896	1.374.896	387.587	836.624	1.208.895
	16.921.660	16.720.884	16.035.819	10.950.000	12.677.066	22.763.337	19.599.303	4.971.825	10.149.871	20.424.332
	34.910.098	36.837.900	36.244.632	25.352.213	32.410.034	39.488.401	45.058.286	12.734.213	24.712.266	44.564.395
	4.950.673	4.789.346	4.869.437	5.554.467	5.559.790	6.624.191	6.688.913	3.236.988	5.326.695	6.823.118
	39.860.771	41.627.246	41.114.069	30.906.680	37.969.824	46.112.592	51.747.199	15.971.201	30.038.961	51.387.513

Source: Sınır İstatistikleri 2011-2021, n.d.

2.2. History of Alanya

Located between the south of the Taurus Mountains and the Mediterranean Sea, Alanya dates back to 20,000 BC. Positioned strategically between Pamphylia and Cilicia in ancient times, the city acquired various names reflective of its geographical significance. Although precise records of its earliest inhabitants remain elusive, historical accounts indicate the arrival of the Hittites in the region around the 16th millennium BC. The Seleucid emperor Antiochus III later seized control of the area between 224 and 188 BC, marking the onset of Byzantine rule. During this era, the city, initially known as

Korakesium, underwent a transformation to Kalanoros. The Byzantine period witnessed the construction of numerous churches in and around the vicinity of Alanya.

The Turkish rule in Alanya commenced with the conquest of the castle by Alaeddin Keykubad I, the Anatolian Seljuk ruler. This period of Turks governance has endured uninterrupted until the present day. The Seljuks used Alanya as the second capital besides their capital Konya and turned the city into an important center through public improvements. The city, which was named Alaiye during the Seljuks period, then came under the rule of Karamanoğulları, Mamluk Sultanate and finally the Ottomans in 1471. The city was named Alanya in 1935 by Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, the founder of the Republic of Türkiye (Kalan & Demir, 2021).

Alanya, which is located 120 km. away from Antalya, has been a multinational society throughout history and is an important tourist center where people from many nations live and a high number of foreign tourists visit.

Alanya was home to the Hellenistic, Roman, Byzantine, Seljuk, Mamluk and Ottoman civilizations and it came to the fore with sea trade for many years, becoming one of the trade centers for Genoese, Venetian, and Florentine merchants. Therefore, Alanya has many historical monuments reflecting these civilizations such as churches, madrasas, inns, baths, traditional houses in addition to its castle and shipyard.

Alanya, which has also stood out with tourism investments in recent years, had a population of 364.180 in 2022 and 13,24% of the population consisted of foreign citizens (Table 3).

Table 3: 2011-2022 Population and Foreign Residents of Alanya

Years	Total Population	Total Number of Foreign Residents	Share (%)
2011	259.787	≈10.000	3,85
2012	264.692	≈10.000	3,78
2013	276.277	11.683	4,23
2014	285.407	11.484	4,02
2015	291.643	10.955	3,76
2016	294.558	8.124	2,76
2017	299.464	12.625	4,22
2018	312.319	20.619	6,60
2019	337.503	27.819	8,24

2020	333.104	32.399	9,72
2021	350.636	44.896	12,80
2022	364.180	48.216	13,24

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

Alanya is 130 km. away from Antalya. Transportation to Alanya is possible by land, air and sea. There are bus services to Alanya from many cities. Air transportation is provided from Antalya and Gazipaşa-Alanya Airports. Those arriving by sea use Alanya Port.

Alanya is 125 km. away from Antalya Airport, and 41 km. away from Gazipaşa-Alanya Airport. Antalya Airport, which serves the most passengers in Türkiye after Istanbul Airport, served a total of 31,1 million incoming and outgoing passengers in 2022, 5,8 million of which were domestic flights and 25,3 million were international passengers. Gazipaşa-Alanya Airport served a total of 682,7 thousand incoming and outgoing passengers in 2022, 421,3 thousand of which were on domestic lines and 261,4 thousand on international lines. In the context of ever-increasing passenger numbers in the Antalya Region, capacity expansion studies have been planned and started at both Antalya and Gazipaşa-Alanya Airports.

Alanya welcomes a high number of foreign tourists every year, and it is also the district where most foreign citizens live permanently compared to the other districts of Türkiye. The majority of the permanent residents came from the Russian Federation, Germany, and North European countries in the 2000s while the majority consists of Russian, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Iran and German citizens to this day (Table 4).

Table 4: 2013-2022; Foreign Population According to Nationalities

Nationalities /Years	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Russian Fed.	3.181	2.483	2.367	1.673	2.530	4.293	6.840	10.360	15.081	18.731
Ukraine	756	n/a	595	423	546	851	1.177	n/a	2.615	6.851
Kazakhstan	295	n/a	n/a	242	362	705	1.273	2.836	4.441	3.603
Germany	948	2.583	2.130	1.339	1.735	1.954	2.308	2.380	3.108	3.066
Iraq	34	n/a	503	820	1.808	3.377	3.748	3.480	3.825	2.924
Iran	168	n/a	660	686	1.102	2.348	2.576	2.400	3.711	2.773
Jordan	4	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	823	1.349	n/a	1.097	863

Kyrgyzstan	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	862	653
Sweden	453	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	700	642
Netherlands	536	783	578	429	500	592	662	n/a	678	633
Azerbaijan	497	n/a	n/a	277	320	464	714	n/a	823	626
Norway	466	n/a	347	239	306	443	612	n/a	537	477
Finland	339	n/a	327	n/a	256	n/a	n/a	n/a	407	348
Denmark	455	n/a	350	218	255	n/a	n/a	n/a	370	342
Others	2.656	5.295	3.098	1.778	2.905	4.769	6.560	10.943	7.503	5.684
Total	11.683	11.484	10.955	8.124	12.625	20.619	27.819	32.399	44.896	48.216

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023).

3. METHOD

This study employs a systematic approach to examine tourism trends in Alanya spanning the last decade. Data were collected from official reports, government publications, and databases. The data source employed is the Türkiye's Ministry of Culture and Tourism, renowned for providing authoritative information regarding foreign visitor arrivals, their nationalities, and expenditure patterns. Additionally, this study draws upon other sources, including reports from esteemed international organizations such as the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), as well as insights from the Alanya Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ALTSO).

To provide a clear overview of the data, descriptive statistics is used which illustrates key patterns in the data, such as the average number of foreign visitors, seasonal variations, and spending differences. Qualitative data from academic literature, government reports, and news sources also are analyzed to us understand political crises in Alanya and the responses of local authorities. By combining these quantitative and qualitative data, this research aim provides a comprehensive understanding of how political crises and the Covid-19 pandemic have impacted Alanya's tourism. This research sheds light on how the tourism industry has adapted to challenges and disruptions.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. ANALYSIS OF TOURISM ACTIVITIES IN ALANYA

4.1.1. Development of Tourism in Alanya

Tourism activities in Alanya started in the 1950s as in the rest of the world. Alanya, which is one of the most beautiful shores of the Mediterranean Sea, has many bays, beaches, plateaus, woodlands and caves. During those years, Damlataş cave in the city center was an important factor in tourism activities. As it was found out that the cave was good for asthma patients, a large number of people from Türkiye began to visit Alanya. However, tourism activities were limited as there were few hotels at that time and the construction of new accommodation facilities was delayed until 1960s. New facilities began to be built intensively and boarding house activities improved after the 1970s.

The length of the beaches in Alanya, which has one of the longest coastlines of Türkiye, is about 70 kilometers. Thanks to the advantage provided by the Mediterranean climate, sea tourism rose to prominence and the number of foreign tourists started to increase after the 1980s. Tourism became diversified because of increased sports events and national/international conference and symposium activities in addition to sea tourism in the 1990s. Those developments have increased the number of domestic and foreign tourists which resulted in an increase in the number of accommodation facilities in Alanya over the years.

Alanya is a district with a very different tourism diversity. However, sea, sand and sun tourism still remain at the forefront. The visitor influx begins in May and lasts until mid-November. The season ended in September in previous years, but it has been extended due to the fact that visitors preferring Egypt in September, October, and November turned to Antalya/Alanya as the visitor influx to Egypt almost came to a standstill after the Arab Spring. However, it is highly possible that the season could end in September again due to the normalization in Egypt.

In fact, this is a well-known fact for the whole Türkiye that the tourism season is limited to 6 months as the tourism diversity is not at the desired level. The number of visitors is very low during the winter season causes many accommodation facilities to remain closed during these months.

Almost all foreign visitors coming for sea, sand and sun tourism come through package tour services of tour operators. Package tours include round-trip flight tickets and accommodation costs. Almost all accommodation facilities offer services with the “all inclusive” system. It is a known fact that visitors usually stay at the accommodation facility and do not go downtown.

Winter tourism is also expected to begin with the improvements to be made at Akdağ Ski Center that is 45 km away from Alanya (Sarı, 2010).

4.1.2. Overview of the Last Decade Statistics of Foreign Tourism

The Antalya area where Alanya is located is one of the most important tourism centers of Türkiye and 30% of the total foreign visitors in the country visit this area (Table 5). The area receives an influx of visitors especially in summer. Approximately one third of the foreign visitors of Antalya come to Alanya. The share of foreign visitors to Alanya within the country is about 10 percent. Germans make up the majority of foreign visitors to Antalya while Russians mostly prefer Alanya.

Table 5: 2011-2022; Türkiye/Antalya/Alanya - Number of Foreign Visitors

Years	Türkiye	Antalya	Alanya	Share of Antalya in Türkiye (%)	Share of Alanya in Antalya (%)	Share of Alanya in Türkiye (%)
2011	31.456.076	10.464.425	2.767.839	33,27	26,45	8,80
2012	31.782.832	10.298.769	3.104.280	32,40	30,14	9,77
2013	34.910.098	11.120.730	2.696.939	31,86	24,25	7,73
2014	36.837.900	11.498.519	3.901.699	31,21	33,93	10,59
2015	36.244.632	10.874.093	3.046.338	29,99	28,01	8,40
2016	25.352.213	5.952.496	1.423.349	23,48	23,91	5,61
2017	32.410.034	9.482.050	2.130.639	29,27	22,47	6,57
2018	39.488.401	12.438.822	3.852.812	31,50	30,97	9,76
2019	45.058.286	14.650.481	4.522.395	32,51	30,87	10,04
2020	12.734.213	3.256.568	843.100	25,57	25,89	6,62
2021	24.712.266	8.737.168	2.453.938	35,36	28,09	9,93
2022	44.564.395	12.818.472	4.025.377	28,76	31,40	9,03

Source: Sınır İstatistikleri 2011-2021, n.d; ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

As can be seen Table 5, the number of foreign visitors to Antalya and Alanya, which increased steadily between 2017 and 2019, decreased in half because of the airplane crisis with Russia in 2015. This crisis also negatively affected the total number of foreign visitors to Türkiye.

A Su-24 fighter jet belonging to the Russian Air Force was shot down by a Türkiye's F-16 fighter jet near the Syrian border on 24 November 2015. Although Türkiye claimed

that the Russian plane made a border violation and had to be shot down because it did not stop despite repeated warnings, the Russian side claimed that there was no border violation. The Russian Federation, which already had a disagreement with Türkiye on the Ukraine, Crimea and Syria issues, began to take steps that would bring its relations with Türkiye to a standstill due to the latest development and imposed a number of economic sanctions against Türkiye. Energy (natural gas) import, fresh fruit and vegetable export, tourism and air transport were severely affected by those sanctions. The political crisis between Türkiye and the Russian Federation continued until mid-2016, the relations started to get better, and the crisis ended after it was found out after the coup attempt that took place on 15 July that the Russian airplane was shot down by the coup plotters in order to create a political crisis. However, since Russian visitors stopped coming to Türkiye during the crisis, the number of foreign visitors especially in the Antalya area decreased considerably during that period (İmanbeyli, 2015).

Another event that had a negative impact on tourism activities both in Europe and in Türkiye is that Thomas Cook, the 178-year-old British operator that brought many visitors to Türkiye went bankrupt. However, the effects of the bankruptcy could not be fully determined due to the Covid-19 pandemic that began in late 2019. Some other tour operators also went bankrupt in 2020. Airline companies significantly reduced the capacity of seats they offered because there were not enough passengers due to restrictions. Revenue-scheduled passenger kilometers decreased by 70% in domestic flights and 85% in international flights, 70% in total around the World (IATA, 2021; ICAO, 2021). In 2020, the number of foreign tourist coming to Türkiye also decreased by 71,7%.

Foreign visitors usually enter Antalya and Alanya by airlines. Airline entries are made from Antalya Airport and Gazipaşa-Alanya Airport while sea entries are made from ports in Antalya and Alanya. Foreign visitor entries to Alanya usually take place through Antalya. Statistical information is given below (Table 6) about foreign visitors who came to Antalya by air and sea from 2011 to 2020 (Ministry of Culture and Tourism/Türkiye, 2011-2022).

According to Table 6 showing the transportation preferences of foreign visitors;

- (1) Antalya area, which also includes Alanya, is home to approximately 32% of the total foreign visitors coming to Türkiye.
- (2) Almost 99% of foreign visitors coming to Antalya prefer airlines.
- (3) There was a steady increase in the number of foreign visitors who came by airlines between 2011 and 2014 but there was a partial decrease in 2015 and up to 50% decrease in 2016 (the reason for the decrease between 2014 and 2016 is the crisis with Russia). The number of foreign visitors started to

increase in 2017 after the Russian crisis ended and the increase continued in 2018 and 2019.

- (4) But, in 2020 the number of foreign tourist coming to Antalya decreased by more than 70% due to the Covid-19 pandemic. But, after the Pandemic, it started to rise again, approaching to 2019 levels.

Table 6: 2011-2022; Foreign Visitors Arriving in Antalya by Means of Transport

Years	Air	Sea	Total	Share/Türkiye
2011	10.277.517	186.908	10.464.425	33,27
2012	10.113.113	185.656	10.298.769	32,40
2013	10.905.129	215.601	11.120.730	31,86
2014	11.322.211	176.308	11.498.519	31,21
2015	10.698.227	175.866	10.874.093	29,99
2016	5.887.339	65.157	5.952.496	23,48
2017	9.417.599	64.451	9.482.050	29,26
2018	12.405.488	33.334	12.438.822	31,50
2019	14.605.259	45.222	14.650.481	32,51
2020	3.253.370	3.298	3.256.568	25,57
2021	8.735.205	1.963	8.737.168	35,36
2022	12.757.742	60.730	12.818.472	28,76

Source: Sınır İstatistikleri 2011-2021, n.d.

According to Table 7 showing the transportation preferences of foreign visitors coming to Alanya;

- (1) Approximately 95% of foreign visitors coming directly to Alanya prefer the airlines.
- (2) The crisis with Russia that took place in 2015 and 2016 caused almost 50% decrease in 2016,
- (3) There was a significant increase in the number of foreign visitors arriving at Gazipaşa-Alanya Airport between 2011 and 2015 but there was up to 50% decrease during the Russian crisis, the number took a turn for the better in 2018 after a slight increase in 2017, but after a significant increase in 2018, it decreased again in 2019.

- (4) In 2020; air and sea (transit) passengers coming directly to Alanya decreased by almost %90,
- (5) After the Pandemic, sea and air passengers started to rise again in 2021 and 2022.

Table 7: 2011-2022; Foreign Visitors Directly Arriving to Alanya by Means of Transport

Years	Alanya (Sea)	Gazipaşa-Alanya Airport (Air)	Total
2011	44.342	3.480	47.822
2012	35.540	37.607	73.147
2013	58.215	121.760	179.975
2014	19.283	200.985	220.268
2015	22.796	249.500	272.296
2016	9.376	153.798	163.174
2017	12.423	173.850	186.273
2018	5.076	312.740	317.816
2019	15.109	298.390	313.499
2020	381	29.703	30.084
2021	91	109.606	109.697
2022	5.203	132.272	137.475

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

A look at the nationalities of foreign visitors to the Antalya area indicates that Russians and Germans have been at the top in recent years. According to Table 8;

- (1) Foreign visitors coming to Antalya since 2011 mostly consist of Germans and Russians and these two countries are followed by the United Kingdom, Ukraine, Poland, and the Netherlands.
- (2) The number of Russian visitors decreased partially in 2015 and dramatically in 2016 due to the crisis with Russia.
- (3) There was also a significant decrease in the number of German visitors following the political crisis with Germany in 2017.
- (4) Also, there was a dramatic decrease in the number of Ukrainian visitors in 2022 due to the war between Russia.
- (5) Most of the foreigners who came to Antalya in 2022 were from Russian, German and United Kingdom.

Table 8: 2012-2022; Distribution of Foreigners Arriving in Antalya (Total) by Countries (over 50.000/2019)

Countries/ Years	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Austria	232.657	231.144	229.153	197.447	80.883	50.693	85.089	118.263	11.490	47.772	129.932
Belarus	80.242	127.283	142.471	138.615	71.092	165.283	163.855	169.342	63.217	145.459	123.172
Belgium	249.725	268.454	262.972	244.625	145.891	137.426	185.600	199.685	12.533	77.397	191.812
Czech Rep.	157.992	147.327	151.704	135.618	47.037	83.711	163.442	227.844	2.718	62.411	220.991
Denmark	202.268	216.947	201.106	218.591	184.447	139.730	182.989	191.083	10.840	39.656	211.414
Finland	117.818	133.222	134.783	137.221	74.856	57.410	80.496	89.454	5.373	13.079	74.450
France	252.210	221.751	188.952	119.280	54.135	63.082	91.774	132.085	24.238	75.965	150.545
Germany	2.883.909	2.831.583	2.932.418	3.150.524	2.019.298	1.696.557	2.308.709	2.673.063	346.206	1.267.497	2.822.451
Iran	70.394	32.548	105.020	108.611	87.188	102.608	70.021	77.528	7.080	62.389	136.088
Iraq	7.220	8.486	11.513	28.218	15.577	47.043	45.911	51.950	3.074	22.777	41.920
Israel	27.333	83.202	92.273	106.465	169.628	174.095	169.946	191.766	20.571	45.548	278.347
Kazakhstan	224.296	260.683	269.487	268.804	126.132	238.344	242.670	234.099	39.834	211.725	357.553
Lithuania	41.258	55.204	68.632	70.212	73.766	98.033	150.955	175.367	2.487	96.209	206.476
Netherlands	528.620	547.220	492.396	501.957	350.209	274.640	388.153	434.754	27.986	132.427	443.833
Norway	300.422	301.506	208.300	191.772	100.301	57.188	91.949	145.130	8.048	17.181	110.439
Poland	213.547	207.093	245.045	241.784	101.485	169.652	400.106	554.995	90.571	416.924	765.072
Romania	83.085	78.043	84.809	98.956	90.827	116.775	194.830	252.692	44.526	165.283	292.466
Russia	2.780.495	3.335.858	3.487.171	2.839.415	492.564	3.804.664	4.778.524	5.582.735	1.509.637	3.586.908	3.033.538
Slovakia	97.490	99.805	103.808	111.727	41.995	77.055	121.407	170.646	2.590	26.705	155.744
Sweedden	348.086	379.731	355.989	336.240	147.323	98.429	157.765	208.079	14.260	42.999	187.457
Switzerland	159.390	168.176	182.973	168.328	78.216	71.892	106.617	129.212	50.366	87.067	161.197
Ukraine	326.982	385.319	287.020	317.989	576.634	717.539	714.882	803.676	557.743	1.271.673	138.260
U. Kingdom	408.961	444.376	450.081	461.592	346.873	376.728	634.175	719.087	211.880	82.796	1.147.442
Others	504.369	555.769	810.443	680.102	476.139	663.473	908.957	1.117.946	189.400	739.321	1.437.873
Total	10.298.769	11.120.730	11.498.519	10.874.093	5.952.496	9.482.050	12.438.822	14.650.481	3.256.568	8.737.168	12.818.472

Source: Sınır İstatistikleri 2012-2022, n.d.

Table 9 and Table 10 below show the distribution of foreign tourists arriving in Alanya by sea and air according to their nationalities. According to Table 9;

- (1) It is certain that arrivals in Alanya by sea are based on the destination preferences of companies that bring tourists with high-capacity ships.
- (2) The tourists were mostly British, American, Italian, German and French between 2011 and 2013 but the number of Italian and French tourists

decreased after 2014, Americans decreased after 2015 and the Germans decreased after 2016.

- (3) The majority of tourist arriving by sea travel were British, French and Germans in 2019,
- (4) In 2020, 2021 and 2022 marine tourism almost stopped due to the Pandemic, and in 2023, it was 5.203, which is only one-third of the 2019 level.

Table 9: 2011-2022; Distribution of Foreign Visitors Arriving in Alanya (by Sea) by Nationalities

Count ries/ Years	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Austria	273	381	292	52	37	7	16	3	21	149	91	5.203
Belarus	2	4	78	-	4	8	2	21	4			
Belgium	255	377	575	61	47	6	8	13	47			
Czech Rep.	24	33	25	6	4	2	-	-	7			
Denmark	141	77	144	10	12	11	7	72	44			
Finland	33	23	27	1	9	3	1	42	20			
France	3.878	3.135	3.299	31	310	3	27	39	547			
German	2.742	5.349	5.282	1.629	1.385	395	494	123	476			
Iran	339	27	25	13	4	-	7	39	15			
Iraq	7	13	23	-	-	-	135	127	106			
Israel	51	32	1.138	9	13	3	26	10	7			
Italy	7.676	3.207	5.266	52	48	28	38	9	36			
Kazakhstan	14	3	5	-	-	-	1	54	43			
Lithuania	22	14	41	3	3	13	31	8	14			
Netherlands	236	335	1.139	103	46	15	3	35	36			
Norway	95	159	128	16	9	2	5	94	67			
Poland	154	49	189	41	33	14	21	2	42			
Romania	39	38	117	27	26	9	22	11	51			
Russian	184	125	209	51	66	14	41	177	128			
Slovakia	11	7	18	6	2	-	2	-	2			
Sweden	169	54	162	17	25	4	11	55	32			
Switzerland	426	152	235	64	58	19	27	10	24			
TRN Cyprus	892	513	338	13	10	3	12	987	314			
Ukraine	17	68	69	67	33	2	34	41	35			
U. Kingdom	19.537	13.606	26.462	13.663	16.206	7.823	8.373	112	9.682			
USA	4.069	3.491	3.943	1.443	1.169	154	71	51	91			

Others	3.056	4.268	8.986	1.905	3.237	838	2.761	5.809	4.396			
Total	44.342	35.540	58.215	19.283	22.796	9.376	12.176	7.944	16.287	149	91	5.203

Source: According to ALTSO Economic Reports, 2011-2022.

The nationalities of passengers arriving at Gazipasa-Alanya Airport, which is the nearest airport to Alanya (app. 40 km.), are given in Table 10, and;

- (1) In 2022, the effect of the Pandemic ended and the airport's international passenger traffic exceeded 2019 levels.
- (2) In recent years, flights to the airport have been carried out by Russian, Danish, Finnish, Lithuanian, Dutch and Iranian airlines.
- (3) Although the airport has been served mainly by Russian tourist since its opening, the number of Russian tourist arriving in 2022 has decreased significantly due to the Russian-Ukraine war. Similarly, tourist arrivals from Ukraine have stopped in 2022.
- (4) The number of foreign visitors from other nationalities is low.

Table 10: 2011-2022; Distribution of Foreigners Arriving in Gazipasa-Alanya Airport by Countries

Countries/ Years	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Austria	3	5	22	317	635	18	13	34	221	0	0	0
Belarus	-	1	10	67	104	54	1.064	1.324	1.510	0	0	0
Belgium	18	4.074	8.221	8.850	8.637	2.247	1.053	1.548	1.578	0	0	0
Czech Rep.	-	4	173	90	178	13	4	47	191	0	0	0
Denmark	-	6.631	20.761	19.624	40.134	50.916	21.412	29.419	31.140	0	1.690	26.505
Finland	-	10	138	10.535	23.801	18.722	19.998	24.723	32.669	4.911	11.502	27.726
France	-	287	552	1.133	988	104	53	260	524	0	0	0
German	14	80	5.722	48.598	49.744	13.512	11.917	20.799	16.098	12.204	0	0
Iran	4	46	3	3.953	624	727	102	176	2.475	593	13.963	10.596
Iraq	-	2	33	60	44	37	23	43	127	0	0	0
Italy	4	37	83	331	373	58	38	124	171	0	0	0
Kazakhstan	-	5	5	57	47	15	147	248	431	0	0	0
Lithuania	-	2	568	7.392	7.886	6.812	9.934	16.566	19.691	0	6.012	20.707
Netherlands	3.398	23.157	38.298	55.515	65.102	36.781	16.122	17.371	20.455	0	0	0
Norway	-	2.415	15.009	19.847	21.406	14.680	5.758	13.893	20.889	1.107	4.270	16.050
Poland	7	42	3.114	377	479	227	161	17.098	364	0	0	0
Romania	-	19	31	108	150	51	20	2.768	2.463	890	0	0

Russian	1	19	97	382	520	343	80.427	150.413	116.829	20.450	39.397	6.244
Slovakia	-	1	15	24	47	4	6	80	29	0	0	0
Sweden	3	451	18.381	19.394	21.908	6.385	2.450	5.619	15.176	0	4.168	5.110
Switzerland	-	-	12	78	89	25	12	26	35	0	0	0
Ukraine	-	2	38	119	159	71	627	1.326	799	0	13.246	0
U. Kingdom	9	35	133	377	432	278	116	589	1.043	0	0	0
USA	3	7	57	89	129	62	26	584	172	0	0	0
Others	161	275	10.284	3.668	5.884	1.656	2.367	7.662	13.310	98.550	205.212	233.783
Total	3.480	37.607	121.760	200.985	249.500	153.798	173.850	312.740	298.390	138.705	299.460	346.721

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

4.2. Accommodation Facilities in Alanya

If the airplane crisis with the Russian Federation in 2016 is not taken into account, the total number of rooms and bed capacity has been increasing in parallel with the steadily increasing number of visitors to Alanya since 2011. As can be seen in Table 11, the number of accommodation facilities was around 650 between 2011 and 2020. The number of rooms increased from 70.199 in 2011 to 83.334 in 2020. Similarly, the number of beds, which rose from 157.885 to 182.526 in 2020. But, because of the Covid-19 pandemic almost the half of the accommodation facilities remain closed about two years. Due to the uncertainty, tourism investments have paused and there has been no significant change in the room and bad capacities in 2021 and 2022.

Table 11: 2011-2022; Number of Accommodation Facilities, Rooms and Beds in Alanya

Years	Number of Accommodation Facilities	Number of Rooms	Number of Beds
2011	678	70.199	157.875
2012	677	73.685	164.651
2013	614	74.434	163.968
2014	642	76.431	168.800
2015	652	84.835	186.971
2016	662	86.437	190.320
2017	637	81.602	176.369
2018	619	81.167	176.993
2019	631	82.350	180.202
2020	632	83.334	182.526

2021	638	83.054	182.332
2022	621	82.518	179.654

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

4.3. Local and Foreign Visitors Staying in Alanya

When we look at the number of visitors staying at accommodation facilities in Alanya between 2011 and 2022 (Table 12); although there was a steady increase until 2015, there was a partial decrease in 2016 and up to 50% decrease in 2017 after the airplane crisis with the Russian Federation. This reveals the importance of the Russian market for Alanya very clearly. Although the total number of staying visitors increased in 2018 and 2019 but it decreased up to %65 in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. 2020 was almost a disastrous year for tourism agencies in Alanya. But, after the Pandemic, the number of tourists increased rapidly in 2021 and 2022, and exceeded the levels of 2019.

Table 12: Alanya; 2011-2022-Number of Domestic and Foreign Visitors Staying at Accommodation Facilities in Alanya

Years	Number of National Visitors	Number of Foreign Visitors	Total Visitors
2011	504.223	2.767.839	3.272.062
2012	513.604	3.104.280	3.617.884
2013	790.561	2.696.939	3.487.500
2014	696.943	3.901.699	4.598.642
2015	1.684.138	3.046.338	4.730.476
2016	1.327.528	1.423.349	2.750.877
2017	731.801	2.434.200	3.166.001
2018	1.037.510	4.642.849	5.680.359
2019	868.495	5.825.161	6.693.656
2020	729.739	1.733.996	2.463.735
2021	1.277.702	4.260.995	5.538.697
2022	1.157.239	6.923.069	8.080.308

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

Table 13 shows how the number of Russian visitors staying at accommodation facilities in Alanya decreased dramatically in 2016. The number of Russian visitors increased rapidly in 2017, 2018 and 2019 and it accounted for 43% of the total foreign visitors in 2019. The second place was held by German visitors by 16%. In 2020; Russian, Ukrainian and Germans were at the top. Considering the profile of foreign visitors to Alanya, Germans were in the lead until 2015 while the number of Russian visitors has rapidly increased and its share in the total has exceeded 40 percent since 2017.

According to 2019 accommodation data, the proportion of Russian and German visitors in total foreign tourists is close to 60 percent. This shows that the Alanya tourist market mostly consists of Russian and German visitors and when problems experienced in these two markets cause significant loss of visitors for Alanya. Political crises experienced with the Russian Federation cause a significant decrease in the total number of foreign visitors to Alanya. Although the density of Russian and German tourists continued in 2021 and 2022, their proportion in the total international tourists has decreased to 40%.

Table 13: Alanya; 2013-2022 - Number of Foreign Visitors Staying at Accommodation Facilities in Alanya

Countries/ Years	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Russian Fed.	811.809	810.254	607.889	91.754	1.096.909	1.972.572	2.482.480	960.221	1.862.723	1.648.593
Germany	732.190	923.035	1.131.436	596.874	464.688	824.364	932.300	149.072	555.615	1.359.045
Poland	105.347	97.101	62.098	32.432	73.747	263.416	394.184	86.632	362.190	661.744
Ukraine	59.744	38.145	34.759	68.231	134.948	170.487	191.984	247.638	572.933	80.741
Denmark	84.814	472.319	77.398	103.784	94.491	188.793	180.245	5.805	31.410	271.949
UK	57.482	52.973	70.554	42.034	74.313	151.725	180.150	66.922	25.546	693.868
Netherlands	119.085	236.345	158.408	61.362	66.752	127.507	159.621	8.637	55.857	219.726
Check Rep.	79.215	65.751	60.930	12.414	30.176	99.056	156.728	2.063	54.746	153.738
Sweden	116.639	456.353	108.388	83.485	60.750	117.493	147.343	8.669	22.016	185.773
Lithuania	36.949	64.055	46.541	23.734	43.416	93.724	130.461	1.107	91.346	185.114
Finland	91.842	123.154	42.099	63.221	50.264	77.766	103.057	7.054	12.571	111.577
Romania	22.115	61.216	42.113	14.222	19.869	57.909	91.705	15.133	62.926	157.108
Norway	93.200	112.473	41.963	35.050	18.239	49.638	75.127	8.051	10.133	95.280
Belarus	29.093	19.686	28.428	13.129	39.338	76.858	85.888	43.447	115.777	76.209
Others	257.408	368.839	533.334	181.623	166.300	371.541	513.888	123.545	371.206	1.022.604
Total	2.696.939	3.901.699	3.046.338	1.423.349	2.434.200	4.642.849	5.825.161	1.733.996	4.260.995	6.923.069
National	790.561	696.943	1.684.138	1.327.528	731.801	1.037.510	868.495	729.739	1.277.702	1.157.239

G. Total	3.487.500	4.598.642	4.730.476	2.750.877	3.166.001	5.680.359	6.693.656	2.463.735	5.538.697	8.080.308
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Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

One of the important findings that emerged from this study is that the majority of visitors coming to Alanya are foreigners, and native visitors only constitutes %15 of the total.

4.4. Tourism Revenues and Economic Contribution of Alanya

Although the number of tourists coming to Türkiye is high, tourism income remains relatively low compared to other countries. The reason for this is that the majority of incoming foreign tourists are from middle- and low-income groups, depending on the countries they come from (Tonbil, 2019).

The expenditures of visitors to Alanya indicate that the expenditure of 700-800 US Dollars per person between 2011 and 2019. After 2020, it has increase to 900-1.000 US Dollars per person.

As can be seen from Table 14, Alanya's tourism income decreased by %58 as a result of the decrease in the number of tourist due to the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020. After the Pandemic, with the increase in the number of tourists, Alanya reached to the highest tourism income in 2022 in her history.

Table 14: Alanya; 2011-2022: Distribution of Tourism Income from Domestic and Foreign Visitors According to Accommodation Statistics

Years	National & Foreigner			Foreigner			National		
	KBOH (Dollar)	Number of Visitors	Total Income (Dollar)	KBOH (Dollar)	Number of Visitors	Total Income (Dollar)	KBOH (Dollar)	Number of Visitors	Total Income (Dollar)
2011	565	3.272.062	1.848.715.030	455	2.767.839	1.259.782.566	1.168	504.223	588.932.464
2012	798	3.617.884	2.887.071.432	725	3.104.280	2.249.688.868	1.241	513.604	637.382.564
2013	824	3.487.500	2.873.700.000	699	2.696.939	1.883.917.628	1.252	790.561	989.782.372
2014	828	4.598.642	3.807.675.576	774	3.901.699	3.020.129.986	1.130	696.943	787.545.590
2015	756	4.730.476	3.576.239.856	638	3.046.338	1.942.625.996	970	1.684.138	1.633.613.860
2016	705	2.750.877	1.939.368.285	450	1.423.349	641.045.901	978	1.327.528	1.298.322.384
2017	700	3.166.001	2.216.200.700	631	2.434.200	1.536.357.571	929	731.801	679.843.129
2018	669	5.680.359	3.800.160.171	617	4.642.849	2.944.214.421	825	1.037.510	855.945.750
2019	751	6.693.656	5.026.928.146	642	5.825.161	4.310.428.021	825	868.495	716.500.125
2020	936	2.463.735	2.305.119.960	930	1.733.996	1.612.089.171	950	729.739	693.030.789

2021	1.028	5.538.697	5.693.780.516	1.014	4.260.995	4.318.973.164	1.076	1.277.702	1.374.807.352
2022	901	8.080.308	7.280.357.508	883	6.923.069	6.116.175.074	1.006	1.157.239	1.164.182.434

Source: ALTSO, 2013; ALTSO, 2014; ALTSO, 2015; ALTSO, 2016; ALTSO, 2017; ALTSO, 2018; ALTSO, 2019; ALTSO, 2020; ALTSO, 2021; ALTSO, 2022; ALTSO, 2023.

According to Alanya economic reports, Alanya's exports indicate that yearly exports amounting to a total of 20 billion US Dollars are realized in general. However, a significant improvement was achieved in 2022 and the total exports approached to 28 billion US Dollars. Since the tourism revenues have exceeded 7 billion Dollars in 2022, it can be said that tourism revenues are of vital importance for Alanya's economy. For this reason, setbacks in tourism activities have severe effects on the Alanya economy and people.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, LIMITATIONS

Literature illustrates that the tourism sector in Türkiye has faced substantial challenges due to political turmoil and the Covid-19 pandemic, resulting in reduced tourist movement, decreased demand, and heightened unemployment within the industry (Çınar & Şener, 2021; Demirel, 2021). Instances of new Covid-19 cases, fatalities, and global apprehension have further dampened industry prospects, although governmental containment efforts and health measures have offered some relief (Koçak et al., 2022). Alanya, which welcomes approximately 8 million foreign visitors a year, is one of the important tourism centers of Türkiye. From an economic point of view, tourism revenues have great importance for Alanya economy. In this context, the economy of Alanya has been significantly affected from the dramatic decrease in the number of Russian visitors as a result of the political crisis with the Russian Federation in 2016. As a result of the health and economic crisis with the Covid-19 pandemic, the tourism sector got severely affected in 2020 and 2021 (Kumudumali, 2020) like all other countries.

Considering the current situation of tourism in Alanya and the negative effects of these crises, it is deemed necessary for those concerned to carry out studies on the following issues for the sustainability of tourism in Alanya.

Considering these facts, there are two important things that must be done for Alanya. The first one is diversifying the number of countries from which foreign tourists come to Alanya and the second one is diversifying tourism. On the other hand, in the context of the increasing number of tourists, capacity expansion investments at Antalya and Gazipaşa-Alanya Airports should be completed in short time and the highway works between Antalya-Alanya and Alanya-Gazipaşa must be completed as soon as possible.

Diversifying the countries of tourists coming to Alanya refers to a large number of tourists from many countries, not only one or two countries. Effects of possible crises will be reduced if tourists come from at least five or six countries by around ten percent each. In order to achieve this, it is necessary to increase the number of tourists by increasing promotional activities in countries with this potential in the current tourist market or to turn to new markets. As to the current market, European Scandinavian countries are countries that first come to mind. It is likely to achieve success in this regard with initiatives and promotions aimed at tour operators. China and Iran stand out as the new markets. Chinese tourists are mostly engaged in cultural tourism. Chinese tourists who come to our country mostly visit the Cappadocia area. Attempts such as introducing the historical background of Alanya could be made to make them stay in Alanya a few nights. Moreover, the appeal can also be increased with gastronomy-centered activities. On the other hand, Iran looks like an emerging market for Alanya. There is an increase in the number of Iranians residing in Alanya. It would be good to make attempts to expand the Iranian market.

The dependence on the sea, sand and sun tourism in Alanya must be decreased through diversification in tourism. Only in this way will it be possible for the tourism season to be extended throughout the year. Gastronomy, nature, sports, and skiing are the first things that come to mind in diversifying tourism. Alanya cuisine has highly rich variety.

Akdağ Ski Resort, which is only 24 kilometers away from Alanya, is a project that has remained on the agenda for 30 years. The snow thickness reaches 1.5 meters in March in Akdağ, creating the ideal environment for skiing. The works have been accelerated lately and a 15 km. long ski resort with 12 ski tracks is about to be finished. Completing these works as soon as possible will make a significant contribution to the tourism diversity.

Alanya's weather conditions make it possible to engage in nature/adventure and sports activities most of the year. Alanya has been hosting international cycling and beach volleyball tournaments for many years.

On the other hand, statistical data indicates that accommodation facilities in Alanya can accommodate up to ten million guests per year considering the current occupancy rates. The capacities of the accommodation facilities must be increased for the coming years.

It is the known necessity that all the relevant institutions and organizations certainly need to cooperate for tourism promotion. The Covid-19 pandemic has clearly

revealed the benefits of digital possibilities in communication and information sharing among people. Digital resources need to be used intensively but consciously for promotion. Here, the expression “consciously” refers to promotions in line with the target market and customer profile. The importance of cooperation will be understood here. It is important to adopt a theme depicting Alanya as a center of attraction and give common messages based on catchy slogans instead of individual promotions. Promotions must draw attention to tourism diversity, especially gastronomic tourism and point out that it is possible to meet the locals as there are many accommodation facilities near the city center as well as gaining new experiences.

The pandemic gave rise to a new and fundamental dimension in the tourism product; health security (Toubes, et al., 2021). In this context, it would be appropriate to give detailed information and assurance that all necessary precautions have been taken at the facilities, attaching due importance to the concept of “safe facility” especially in promotional/marketing activities to be carried out by accommodation facilities.

Another issue is that the Covid-19 pandemic is expected to cause some changes in consumer behavior. Namely, in the new normal period, it is expected that there will be an increase in individual holidays, away from mass groups, in touch with nature and with low participation. This situation can be seen as a disadvantage for our country where mass tourism is intense. It would be appropriate to carry out studies aimed at this (Kaygısız, 2021).

Finally, with the end of the Pandemic, tourism activities returned to normal. However, it is certain that similar pandemics may occur again and it would be appropriate to keep the experiences gained from this pandemic in mind and turn them into achievements for faster reactions and precautions to prepare prevention/implementation plans and to keep these plans up to date.

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